

ORGANIZATION OF DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MODERN EDUCATION BASED ON CLUSTER APPROACH

Nasirova Shaira Narmuradovna - NavSU, Professor of
the Department of "Digital Technologies"

Abstract: *Today, the formation of electronic educational resources, creation of modern educational tools and portals, and further informatization of education are urgent issues in the teaching of computer science. This article highlights the main features of training future computer science teachers in an e-learning environment based on a cluster approach.*

Key words: *computer, multimedia electronic manuals, Internet, electronic database.*

The future of our country depends on our children who are being educated in schools today, on their development as fully developed and well-rounded individuals. Fulfilling this responsible task requires modern teachers to improve their professional skills, understand the essence of advanced pedagogical technologies and use them effectively in their lessons. Nowadays, interest and attention to the use of innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. One of the main reasons for this is that while in traditional education students are taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, modern technologies allow them to search for the knowledge they acquire, independently study and analyze it, and even draw conclusions on their own. The eighth paragraph of the “New Uzbekistan Development Strategy” sets out the tasks of achieving quality education in the country. Over the past few years, a resolution has been adopted “On approval of the Concept for the Development of the Preschool Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” aimed at the healthy and comprehensive development of the

growing generation in our country, and the introduction of effective forms and methods of education into the educational process.

The combination of science and education with production ensures progress in all areas. In this regard, of course, the integration of science, education and production is an important and urgent task. This in itself paves the way for an innovative cluster. The cluster in the education system is aimed at the development of the individual and becoming a mature person, and its connection is that it connects the entire lifelong education chain, which includes processes such as kindergarten, school, lyceum, college, higher education institution, doctoral studies, advanced training. In pedagogical technology, the cluster is a well-thought-out strategy that can be used in the process of individual or group training with students. Clusters create an opportunity to generalize the ideas put forward and find connections between them.

In global educational institutions, mechanisms for the interaction of entities united in clusters and technologies for implementing the cluster approach are being put into practice. In the context of the United Nations "Sustainable Development Goals" and the European Union "European Higher Education Area" Concepts, systematic work is being carried out to develop methods for developing the professional training of future engineers based on a cluster approach, identify promising areas of higher education, and project best practices in the formation and development of professional competencies in the higher education space into the process of organizing and managing education.

The integration of several interrelated activities around a common goal within the framework of a cluster approach requires clear calculations and scientific solutions, scientific, theoretical projects with guaranteed results, and only then will the cluster approach gain the trust of the subjects. The cooperation of educational organizations based on a cluster approach cannot be carried out by issuing

bureaucratic and administrative orders. It can operate effectively based on the voluntary goodwill of the subjects.

The cluster approach to education is an innovative process in our national pedagogy, which includes not only the integration processes between types of education, but also between science, education and production, as well as areas related to innovative management of education, means and forms of education. According to Michael Porter, a professor at Harvard School, an expert in the study of competitive opportunities, clusters should have the following common features:

- the presence of research institutions;
- labor resources;
- competitiveness;
- industry affiliation;
- the presence of special educational institutions, etc.

In pedagogy, the "cluster" method is also called the technology of networks, and this method is understood within the framework of logical thinking and general thinking.

According to international innovative experiences, a cluster approach is recommended to increase the efficiency of education, in which it is important to ensure the continuity of science, education and production, accelerate innovative activities, and eliminate conflicts in the interaction of educational objects and processes. The organization of a mechanism for effective cooperation between participants in the types and processes of education in an educational cluster allows improving the quality of education and successfully developing the competencies of participants in the educational process. The role of integration is important in the implementation of an educational cluster. Integration in education is a factor that increases efficiency, and integration processes are of practical importance. The need to attract all resources to ensure the quality of general education institutions - methodological, scientific, material and financial, technological, information, and

quality education - is precisely realized. In the context of education, integration between types of education is manifested in the organization of innovative models aimed at improving the quality of teaching subjects, by attaching professors, researchers, practitioners, students, and masters of higher education institutions to general education schools.

The rapid development of information and communication technologies, the widespread use of artificial intelligence, digital platforms, online learning systems, and multimedia tools - all this creates the need to introduce new approaches to pedagogical activities. Taking into account the needs of the new generation of students for rapid assimilation of information, flexible thinking, and independent learning, the process of digitization of education is becoming increasingly relevant.

Therefore, by analyzing the theoretical and practical foundations of cluster application in the education system, it is possible to comprehensively update and develop the main features of the region's education quality management, content and structure.

REFERENCES:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated 28.01.2022 on the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. 29.01.2022
2. Mirkasimova M. Principles of integrating academic subjects in distance education. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* VOLUME ISSU1, ISSN 2181-1784 Scientific Journal Impact Factor SJIF 2021: 5.423. P. 959-969.
3. Nasirova Sh.N. The effectiveness of using electronic resources in the digital education system. “Муғаллим ҳам узлуксиз билимлендириў” Илмий-методикалық журнал № 6 2023 жыл., ISSN 2181-7138, Нукус – 2023, 96-102 pp.
4. Nasirova Sh.N., Tillayev M.M. The importance of creating multimedial electronic learning resources. **Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research** is a

scholarly peer reviewed international multidisciplinary Journal, **ISSN: 2776-1010**,
557-559 p.

5. Sh.N.Nasirova, G.J. Jakipova. Principles of organizing development trends of modern education based on a cluster approach. Bulletin news in New Science Society International Scientific Journal, Vol 2 Issue 7, 2025, iyul, Germaniya, 31-33 pp.